

BLOOD PROTEIN FRACTIONS AND RENAL TESTS IN ANIMALS WITH RENAL ARTERY STENOSIS

Arsenova Mukhabat Abdumominovna

Iriskulov Bakhtiyor Uktamovich

Mukhamedova Nurkhan Khalilovna

Tashkent State Medical University,

Kimyo International University in Tashkent

Uzbekistan, Tashkent

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18399765>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 25th January 2026

Accepted: 26th January 2026

Online: 27th January 2026

KEYWORDS

The aim of the study was to investigate changes in blood protein fractions and kidney function tests in animals with renal artery stenosis

ABSTRACT

Renal artery stenosis is a leading cause of renal blood flow impairment, leading to ischemic kidney damage and systemic metabolic changes. Blood flow restriction activates neurohumoral mechanisms, leading to renovascular hypertension and a progressive decline in nephron function. One important area of study in the pathogenesis of renal artery stenosis is assessing changes in protein metabolism and renal function. Impaired liver synthetic function, inflammatory reactions, and the development of proteinuria may be accompanied by changes in the spectrum of protein fractions in the blood. Concurrently, renal function tests, including creatinine, urea, and glomerular filtration rates, allow for an objective assessment of the degree of renal excretory dysfunctions.

Renal artery stenosis is a leading cause of renal blood flow impairment, leading to ischemic kidney damage and systemic metabolic changes. Blood flow restriction activates neurohumoral mechanisms, leading to renovascular hypertension and a progressive decline in nephron function. One important area of study in the pathogenesis of renal artery stenosis is assessing changes in protein metabolism and renal function. Impaired liver synthetic function, inflammatory reactions, and the development of proteinuria may be accompanied by changes in the spectrum of protein fractions in the blood. Concurrently, renal function tests, including creatinine, urea, and glomerular filtration rates, allow for an objective assessment of the degree of renal excretory dysfunction.

This study aims to investigate changes in serum protein fractions and renal function tests in animals with renal artery stenosis. The data obtained will help clarify the metabolic and functional consequences of ischemic kidney injury and substantiate the diagnostic value of these parameters.

The aim of the study was to investigate changes in blood protein fractions and kidney function tests in animals with renal artery stenosis.

Objectives of the study: To determine the total protein content in the blood serum of animals with renal artery stenosis. To study changes in the main protein fractions (albumins, α 1-, α 2-, β - and γ -globulins). To evaluate the parameters of renal tests (creatinine, urea) in

conditions of ischemic kidney damage. To analyze the degree of impairment of glomerular filtration and excretory function of the kidneys.

The following methods were used in the work:

An experimental model of renal artery stenosis created by partial narrowing of the artery lumen in laboratory animals.

A biochemical blood test that includes determination of total protein and protein fractions using electrophoresis.

Evaluation of renal function tests, including measurement of serum creatinine and urea levels.

Calculation of the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) using standard physiological formulas.

Statistical processing of results with determination of the reliability of differences ($p < 0.05$).

Study results. Animals with renal artery stenosis showed significant changes in blood protein levels and renal function parameters. Decreases in total protein and albumin levels were observed, which may be related to impaired protein metabolism and protein loss in the urine. Concurrently, an increase in γ -globulin levels was observed, indicating the activation of inflammatory and immune processes in response to ischemic injury to renal tissue. Renal function tests showed a significant increase in creatinine and urea concentrations in the blood, indicating a decrease in glomerular filtration and a deterioration in renal excretory function.

Thus, renal artery stenosis leads to combined metabolic and functional disorders reflecting the progression of ischemic nephropathy.

Conclusions. Renal artery stenosis is accompanied by changes in blood protein fractions, manifested by decreased albumin and total protein. Elevated γ -globulin levels indicate the development of inflammatory-immune reactions associated with ischemic kidney damage. Increased creatinine and urea levels indicate decreased renal filtration capacity. A comprehensive assessment of blood protein profiles and renal function tests is an informative method for diagnosing functional impairment associated with renal artery stenosis.

The obtained data confirm the importance of biochemical monitoring for the early detection of ischemic nephropathy and prevention of complications.

List of references:

1. Basile D.P., Anderson M.D., Sutton T.A. Pathophysiology of acute kidney injury. *Comprehensive Physiology*. 2012;2: 1303–1353.
2. Betteridge D.J. What is oxidative stress? *Metabolism*. 2000;49(2):3–8.
3. Cadenas E., Davies K.J.A. Mitochondrial free radical generation, oxidative stress, and aging. *Free Radical Biology & Medicine*. 2000; 29:222–230.
4. Himmelfarb J., McMonagle E. Albumin is the major plasma protein target of oxidant stress in uremia. *Kidney International*. 2001; 60 :358–363.
5. Koyner J.L., Sher Ali R., Murray P.T. Antioxidants in the prevention and treatment of acute kidney injury. *Nephron Clinical Practice*. 2008;109:c209–c216.
6. Singbartl K., Joannidis M. Short-term effects of oxidative stress in ischemic kidney injury. *Kidney International*. 2015; 88:2–4.
7. Turrens J.F. Mitochondrial formation of reactive oxygen species. *Journal of Physiology*. 2003; 552:335–344.